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Research Article

**EXPERIENCE INNOVATION IN PRIVATE HOSPITALS IN
TERMS OF AWARENESS ABOUT IT AND ITS APPLICATION**¹Ifrah Saeed, ¹Maryam Saeed, ²Dr. Gohar Mukhtar¹Sir Syed College of Medical Sciences for Girls, Karachi, ²Services Hospital Lahore.**Abstract:**

Objective: The research objective is the evaluation of the perspective of private hospitals regarding experience innovation.

Methods: We conducted this qualification type study in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to May 2018. We interviewed patients and staff taking the help of a semi-structured consultation guide. We examined the employees about what 'innovation' meant, awareness regarding experience innovation, and measurement of EI. We also asked the patients regarding the hospital choice, actual reason for arrival at that specific hospital, and their impressions at the time of leaving it. We examined the EI based on those obtained answers.

Results: We interviewed 87 subjects. Among them, the number of patients and employees was 59% (51) and 41% (36) respectively. The number of male and female subjects was 30% (26) and 70% (61) respectively from (21-75) years' age group. We observed high tendencies of hospitals towards activities of innovation but they confused innovation with novelty.

Conclusions: Making investments without considering EI does not produce targeted results.

Keywords: Experience Innovation (EI), Creativity, Private Hospital (PH), and Novelty.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hospitals are huge complex structures with busy routines requiring huge investments. These structures require to keep high standards and should be competitive. To compete for the hospital sustainability and meet patients' expectations by improving capabilities, a hospital must innovate. Meeting the new market and business requirements through product presentation, implementation, and processing is actual innovation. The innovations mentioned frequently in literature denote process, service, and product innovations. The innovation of experience comes under the sub-title of the process of service. There are various definitions of innovations and we should not confuse it with the invention. The term 'innovation' comes from the Latin word "innovations". We can define it as "the initiation of new methods in an administrative, cultural, and social environment" [1]. OECD (Economic Cooperation and Development) defines it as "implementing a service, product, or process as a method of marketing, which is changed and new; or the introduction of a new organizational method in external affairs or business organizations." Innovation is a new idea that develops its value in the market with a rapid introduction on new services and products creating awareness [2, 3]. Christopher Freeman says, "Failure to innovate means death" [4]. In order to exist in this current competitive business operations, continuous innovation is necessary [4]. Hospital competitions have innovation as the main key as authors claim [5, 6]. To meet patients' requirement, we need a proactive approach in innovation [7]. Completing patients' requirement quickly with better service, improved organizational and administration models are some of the factors of innovations [1]. There are many reasons for innovation such as creative organizational environment, suitability for recognition as a novelist and sustaining this position, hope, and high morale for improved business operation, capability, and profit [8]. Innovation leads to development and economic growth of a country, lifestyle improves which results in increased competition power among hospitals [9]. There are 8 types of innovations; new product, implementation, disorderly strategic, process, business, marketing, experience, and structural innovation [10]. The impression of patients after using a provided service an experience innovation. This experience can fascinate patients may be the effect is ordinary. For example, in better service experience, a technician should operate mammography to shoot even in shorter time instead of showing lack of interest, or rude attitude. This is experience innovation on the part of the receiving the party. In past, religious organisations used to render the hospitals but now surgeons,

physicians, nurses/midwives, and pharmacists who are health professionals render these institutions. The nature of health services is so delicate that even the smallest mistake can lead to dangerous outcomes resulting loss of human life [11]. Innovating hospitals seem difficult at first glance, however, integrating the improvements in medical science continuously in disease diagnosis, treatment, and controlling motivates innovation. But as we know that many other administrations like food, hospitality, technical services etc. make hospitals big business operations implementing innovation. An examination of current health programme transformation shows that Social Security Institution (SSI) agreements increased competition among hospitals by turning hospitals into large investments, increase in chronic patients and prolongation of a societal lifetime. The reasons for high competition in experience innovation in health services are improved technology, easy access to health information and services, health management, and improving service standard qualities.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

We conducted this qualification type study in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from October 2017 to May 2018. We interviewed patients and staff taking the help of a semi-structured consultation guide [12]. We examined the employees about what 'innovation' meant, awareness regarding experience innovation, and measurement of EI. We also asked the patients regarding the hospital choice, actual reason for arrival at that specific hospital, and their impressions at the time of leaving it. We examined the EI based on those obtained answers. Three academicians (not part of the study) sought out the idea/questions for this interview. Among health professionals, we included health managers, physicians, and nurses.

RESULTS:

We interviewed 87 subjects having health professionals and patients of 41% (36) and 59% (51) respectively. The number of men and women was 30% (26) and 70% (61) having an age range of (21 – 75) years. We found these major findings from Private Hospitals:

A hospital reports having services of international standard mentioning a self-productive, friendly, and green environment providing photographs of newborns, accommodations to patients' attendees and relatives, and home-care services. A hospital served patients through robotic surgery with patients' consent and designed a shopping centre inside the hospital (Established since 1989). A hospital provided children's playground, whirlpool bath in patients'

wards, stewardesses in polyclinic service, messages and flowers distribution on special days (Established since 1997). Another hospital provided free car parking, phone calls to discharged patients, five-star hotel services, beautiful decoration with unlimited internet, and optional food menu (Established since 1985). One patient established innovations like long-term physicians' employment, pregnancy training, informative web pages, photo album for babies, and free mammography and scanning on special days (Established since 2002). A hospital organised classical music concert for chemotherapy receiving patients and a high school having a contracted (Established since 1992). Another hospital called their discharged patients, reminded patients for the next appointments, providing information brochures, not saying "No" in the hospital, new-born photos on their website, baby deliveries in room and wheelchairs for discharged patients (Established since 1991). One hospital cleaned admitted patients' clothes and returned them on discharge, and set the rule of "every

job is everyone's job" (Established since 1989). A hospital considered a complaint as a "gift" and appreciated them as "guests" (Established since 1996). The findings we received from fifty-one patients were as follows:

"The services are affordable. The reasons for my satisfaction are attention given to patients with a smile, follow-up, and text/reminders on special days and next appointment." "I like my physician and trust him a lot. My physician takes necessary examinations only. The hospital is hygienic and clean." "Despite high charges, this hospital is my preference because of its accessibility, good attention to patients, and a personal attendee that helps me in completing hospital formalities until my discharge." Evaluating the abovementioned points, we find that hospitals having no EI are preferred only because of the fee, having an affiliation with a physician, trusting the physician, attention given to the patients, accessibility of hospital, and sanitation and hygiene in the hospital.

Table: Details of Population and Gender Distribution

Details		Number (87)	Percentage
Population	Patients	51	59
	Healthcare Professionals	36	41
Gender	Women	61	70
	Men	26	30

DISCUSSION:

Currently, the hospital sector emphasizes improving technology constantly but they do not have a clear

mind regarding using/implementing this new technology on patients. At this point, experience innovation comes forward. We do not see the effects

of large investments, financial resources, and bigger budgets on the services of receivers. Our study shows that sectors like hospitals where profit comes second, a small investment can be of huge value if it is used to complete the requisites correctly. Hospitals are unaware of these novelties and their studies do not guide developments towards innovations rather merely increasing the number of patients. If health-care providers conduct studies on experience innovation in order to find and fulfil the needs of patients, service receivers would experience the due difference in the whole health-care sectors. In this study, nurses' reluctant attitude towards fulfilling a patient's requirement for example playing music during chemotherapy, providing help in completing hospital formalities, and providing services with a smile put the patient in an uncomfortable environment. Patient recognised the quality of the image to be partial instead of the hospital staff. It is very vital for the hospitals to leave a positive image on the patients through their helping behaviour at first part and providing other necessary services like sanitation, hygiene, and pleasant healthy environment.

CONCLUSION:

Making huge investments without considering experience innovation do not provide benefits and required results. Expenses made on unnecessary areas to achieve a lavish expenditure does not improve the quality of service received on the part of health-care receivers. Therefore, experience innovation has vital importance in improving the overall experience of a hospital to achieve the vital purpose of health-care sectors.

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